

Removal of Micropollutants in Municipal Wastewater using TiO₂-Diatomite Composite under UVC Irradiation

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Abstract

This study investigated the effectiveness of the TiO₂-diatomite composite in removing specific micropollutants from municipal wastewater at neutral pH. The findings revealed that although the presence of the TiO₂-diatomite composite led to slightly faster removal of certain micropollutants, it did not have a significant impact on the final concentrations of micropollutants after 4 hours of reaction at low levels compared to the use of UVC alone. However, at high concentrations of micropollutants, the TiO₂-diatomite composite slightly enhanced the removal efficiency of some micropollutants. Specifically, clarithromycin removal increased from 49% to 65%, while ifosfamide removal increased from 5% to 11%.

Keywords: TiO₂-diatomite composite; Photocatalysis; Micropollutants; Municipal Wastewater; Diatomite; Pharmaceuticals

1. Introduction

Micropollutants deriving from pharmaceuticals, personal care products, and industrial chemicals can be found in water bodies at a concerning concentration level for living organisms. Conventional wastewater treatment technologies were insufficient to remove most of the micropollutants (Verlicchi et al., 2010) resulting in a broad spectrum of compounds entering the aquatic environment (Jiang et al., 2013). Recently, Water Europe (WE) which promotes water-related innovation and RTD in Europe, forse to Water-Smart Society in which water sources are managed in such a way that water scarcity and pollution of water are avoided. WE propose to focus RTD to develop innovative water technologies, digital solutions, and models to reduce the impact on natural water resources for secure and long-term resilience, stability, and sustainability concerning water. One of the four main components of the proposed model for a Water Smart society by WE encompasses technology for more advanced and cost-effective solutions to removing all types of pollutants and micropollutants (WE, Water Europe Water Vision 2030). Hence, it is crucial to develop effective, applicable, and low-cost technologies to treat micropollutants that were persistent to conventional treatment systems. There are several technologies used to remove micropollutants in water, such as; advanced oxidation process (H₂O₂-Fe²⁺), peroxonation (H₂O₂/O₃), photochemical (UV-chemicals), and catalyst are promising classes of technologies (Anglada et al. 2009). Titanium dioxide has been widely chosen for the application of photocatalysis processes for water treatment as it showed an excellent ability to generate OH- radicals resulting in the oxidization of pollutants (Zuo et al. 2014). However, the immobilization of TiO₂ into diatomite and its application for micropollutants removal in wastewater have not been explored. The knowledge of the dominant composition of micropollutants presence in municipal wastewater treatment plants and factors affecting the concentrations may help to develop better treatment solutions in tackling environmental issues. This study

aims to investigate the effectiveness of TiO₂-diatomite composite for the degradation of selected micropollutants from pharmaceuticals in municipal wastewater under UVC Irradiation.

2. Material and Methods

The photocatalytic activity of the TiO₂-diatomite composite was investigated to remove micropollutants in municipal wastewater under UVC irradiation. The preparation of TiO₂-diatomite composites was carried out following Hocaoglu et al., (2022) which is a modified method of Wang et al., (2015a). The diatomite (Celite 535) was used as a support material (Figure 1a). Tetrabutyl titanate (C₁₆H₃₆O₄Ti, TBOT, provided by Merck) was used for the preparation of the TiO₂-diatomite composites using sol-gel method. Ethanol (C₂H₅OH) and acetic acid (CH₃COOH) used were analytic grade as purchased for the purification of diatomite. Declophenac was supplied by Sigma Aldrich (Germany). Figure 1a shows the microstructure of diatomite after the purification process at a magnification of 40X.

The photocatalytic activity was investigated at two different concentrations of micropollutants under UVC irradiation using a 6 W mercury lamp ($\lambda = 254$ nm) at 0.2 g/L dosage of Ti-535 composite in a photocatalytic reactor (Figure 1b). To evaluate the direct applicability, the pH of the treated water was not changed. Other test conditions were selected similar to a previous study optimized for the same composite (Hocaoglu et al., 2022). Before UV illumination, the suspension was stirred vigorously for one hour in the dark to establish the absorption-desorption equilibrium. Then was exposed to UVC irradiation for 240 min. The tests were repeated at high concentrations of selected micropollutants, which were added to the biologically treated municipal wastewater sample to represent the highest concentrations in wastewater, as referred to in literature data. Before the micropollutant analysis, the TiO₂-diatomite composite was separated by centrifugation at 6000 rpm (8 min). Liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) was used for detecting micropollutants in the samples.

Figure 1. Photocatalytic degradation of micropollutants using UVC lamp.

3. Results and Discussion

Wastewater sample was obtained from the final discharge of a municipal wastewater treatment plant in Kocaeli, Turkey, and the composition is presented in Table 1. In total, 7 organic micropollutants were selected for this study and the maximum concentration was added to the effluent sample to represent the existence/presence of micropollutants in wastewater as referred to lite-

ature data. The selected micropollutants have been identified as pharmaceutical industry compounds. Physicochemical parameters are indicators of organic contamination in water. COD, total phosphorus and nitrogen, color, and SS are the primary physicochemical parameters as the macro-pollutants of the effluent municipal wastewater treatment plant. Accordingly, total nitrogen and phosphorus were measured at approximately 3 mg/L, COD 84 mg/L, TOC 2.2 mg/L and color value 44 Pt/Co. There are also some heavy metals such as lead, zinc, nickel, tin and chromium in the MWWTP effluent.

Table 1. Characterisation of treated municipal wastewater

Parameter	Concentration
<i>Organic matter</i>	
pH	7.7
TOC (mg/L)	2.2
COD (mg/L)	84
Suspended solids (mg/L)	< 5
Color (Pt/Co)	44
Total nitrogen	2.9
Total phosphorus	2.8
<i>Heavy metals</i>	
Pb (µg/L)	0.4
Zn (µg/L)	138
Ni (µg/L)	90
Sn (µg/L)	15
Cr (µg/L)	3.7
<i>Micropollutants</i>	
Carbamazepine (µg/L)	0.29
Ciprofloxacin (µg/L)	1.50
Clarithromycin (µg/L)	0.11
Sulfametoksazol (µg/L)	0.43
Naproxen (µg/L)	0.54
Tetracycline (µg/L)	0.1
Ifosfamide (µg/L)	0.05

Table 2. Selected organic micropollutants in the study.

Compound	CAS No	Molecular weight (g/mol)	Chemical use groups	Concentration after addition – high concentration (µg/L)*
Carbamazepine	298-46-4	236.3	Psychiatric drug	1.08
Ciprofloxacin	85721-33-1	331.3	Antibiotic	3.90
Clarithromycin	81103-11-9	747.9	Antibiotic	0.12
Sulfametoksazol	723-46-6	253.3	Antibiotic	10.2
Naproxen	22204-53-1	230.3	Anti-inflammatory drug	3.04
Tetracycline	60-54-8	444.4	Antibiotic	2.73
Ifosfamide	3778-73-2	261.1	Chemotherapy drug	0.81

* After addition of pharmaceutical according to the literature range in treated municipal effluent

Both applications using biologically treated municipal wastewater were found to be relatively similar in the final concentration of the selected micropollutants after 4 hours of reaction. However, slightly faster removal was observed in the presence of TiO₂-diatomite composite

even at low concentrations of micropollutants. The removal efficiencies were 98% versus 98% for ciprofloxacin, 71% versus 82% for carbamazepine, and 64% versus 65% for clarithromycin, with and without composite, respectively. For the case of high concentrations of micropollutants, similar performance was observed for some micropollutants with UVc application alone, with the highest removal efficiencies of >95% for sulfamethoxazole, naproxen, and tetracycline and 29% versus 27% for carbamazepine. On the other hand, higher removal efficiencies were observed in the presence of the composite at high concentrations of clarithromycin and ifosfamide, with values of 65% and 11%, as compared to 49% and 5% with only UVc, respectively.

Figure 2. Micropollutant degradation efficiency by photocatalytic oxidation with UV/TiO₂-diatomite and UVc only

Table 3. Treatment results for some organic micropollutants selected in the study

Micropollutant, %	Carbamazepine	Ciprofloxacin	Clarithromycin	Sulfamethoxazole	Naproxen	Tetracycline	Ifosfamide
TiO ₂ -diatomite+UVC	71*/29	98*/98	64*/65	99.9	98.5	95	11
UVC only	82*/27	98*/95	65*/49	99.8	98	96	5

*at low concentration

4. Conclusions

The investigation revealed that UVC irradiation alone effectively removed the investigated micropollutants in biologically treated municipal wastewater at low concentrations. The presence of the TiO₂-diatomite composite did not have a significant impact on removal of micropollutant concentrations at low levels, despite a slight increase in the removal rate of certain pollutants. However, at high concentrations, the TiO₂-diatomite composite showed promise in enhancing micropollutant removal, particularly for clarithromycin and ifosfamide among the tested micropollutants. Investigating, the effects of pH and dosage of the TiO₂-diatomite composite could be considered for future studies to improve removal efficiency. Additionally, it would be beneficial to test the composite with other micropollutants, and endocrine disrupting pollutants that are resistant to degradation.

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